

A SEMI-ANALYTICAL METHOD FOR MEASURING THE STRAIN ENERGY RELEASE RATES OF ELLIPTICAL CRACKS- A NOVEL FINITE FRACTURE MECHANICS-BASED FAILURE CRITERION APPLICATION

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BACKGROUND OVERVIEW & MOTIVATION

- Background (Free-edge effect):

Potential singular localized three-dimensional stress fields arise in the vicinity of interfaces between dissimilar laminate layers.

- Motivation:

1. Although free-edge effect has been under scientific investigation for more than 5 decades, it remains an open problem to predict the stress concentrations and associated delamination accurately.
2. Numerous closed-form, semi-analytical, and numerical methods have been proposed, however, each have documented either limitations or are computationally expensive.

Free-edge effect [1]

AIMS & OBJECTIVES

- To develop a method to obtain interfacial fracture parameters in a symmetric/hybrid stacked laminates.
- Utilising the above parameters to propose a failure criterion based on Finite Fracture Mechanics (FFM).

INTERFACIAL STRAIN ENERGY RELEASE RATE

- Preliminary dimensional analysis for a general two-ply bi-material system.

$$G = G \left((\sigma_\infty), (a, b, \text{location}), (\phi), (h, H, W, L), (E_1^s, E_2^s, G_{12}^s, \nu_{12}^s, \nu_{23}^s), (E_1^m, E_2^m, G_{12}^m, \nu_{12}^m, \nu_{23}^m) \right)$$

$$G_i(\omega, \mu, \eta, \alpha, \beta, \phi) = \frac{\sigma_\infty^2 h}{E'} \psi_i^2(\omega, \mu, \eta, \alpha, \beta, \phi) \quad i \in \{x, y, z\}$$

Where ψ_i is non-dimensional correction factor,

- $\omega = \mathfrak{I}_m / \mathfrak{I}^*$ ← normalised material parameters (*traces* [2])
- $\mu = \mathfrak{I}_s / \mathfrak{I}^*$ ← reference value (average 3D trace of CFRP considered)
- \mathfrak{I}^* ←
- $E' = \mathfrak{I}_m \cdot \omega / \mu$ ← equivalent modulus

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} C_{xx} & C_{xy} & C_{xy} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{yx} & C_{yy} & C_{yz} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{yx} & C_{zy} & C_{yy} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 2C_{ss} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2C_{ss} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2C_{zz} \end{bmatrix}$$

- $\alpha = a/H$ ← normalised crack semi-axes
- $\beta = b/H$ ←
- $\eta = H/h$ ← normalised geometric parameter
- ϕ ← polar angle along the crack front

MODE-MIXITY ALONG CRACK FRONT

- For a given material (ω, μ) and thickness η parameter, mode-mixity ratios are dependant on polar angle ϕ & crack profile (α, β) :

$$M_{II}(\phi, \alpha, \beta) = \frac{G_{II}}{G_I + G_{II} + G_{III}}$$

$$M_{III}(\phi, \alpha, \beta) = \frac{G_{III}}{G_I + G_{II} + G_{III}}$$

Influence of crack parameters α and β on norm. ERR

- ERR distribution is computed using 3D-VCCT (Abaqus in-built) for metal/90.

Titanium – Grade 2

CFRP 90°

Dependence of norm. ERRs on α and β is due to not only crack profile but ply orientation also.

$$\psi_T^2 = \psi_1^2 + \psi_2^2 + \psi_3^2$$

FRACTURE CRITERION SPECTRUM

Strength of materials	Weak stress singularity and absence of a crack (flaw)	Fracture mechanics
<p data-bbox="290 411 647 448">No stress singularity</p> <ul data-bbox="1880 919 2423 1058" style="list-style-type: none"> When energy release rate is greater than the fracture toughness $h(\mathcal{G}_g(\Delta a), \mathcal{G}_c) \geq 1$		

[3] Leguillon D. Strength or toughness? A criterion for crack onset at a notch. Eur J Mech A/Solids 2002;21:61–72.

INCREMENTAL ENERGY RELEASE RATE (IERR)

- Griffth's ERR: differential form

$$\mathcal{G} = -\frac{d\pi}{da} \quad \text{where } a \text{ is crack length}$$

- Incremental ERR: incremental form

$$\bar{\mathcal{G}} = -\frac{\Delta\pi}{\Delta a}$$

- Therefore, $\bar{\mathcal{G}}_i$ can be calculated from integral average of \mathcal{G}_i

$$\bar{\mathcal{G}}_i = \frac{1}{\Delta a} \int_0^{\Delta a} \mathcal{G}_i da = \frac{\sigma_\infty^2 h}{E'} \frac{1}{A} \iint_0^A \psi_i^2 da = \frac{\sigma_\infty^2 h}{E'} \Lambda_i$$

$\Lambda \longrightarrow$ norm. IERR

$\bar{\mathcal{G}}_i$ is IERR for mode i , gives energy rate required to nucleate a crack of area A (area of semi-ellipse).

INTERLAMINAR STRESSES COMPUTATION

- Interlaminar stresses computed using Abaqus for a general two-ply bi-material system :

Dimensional analysis

$$\sigma = \sigma \left((\sigma_\infty), (y), (H, h), (E_1^s, E_2^s, G_{12}^s, \nu_{12}^s, \nu_{23}^s), (E_1^m, E_2^m, G_{12}^m, \nu_{12}^m, \nu_{23}^m) \right)$$

$$\sigma_{iz}(\omega, \mu, \eta, y') = \sigma_\infty \chi_{iz}(\omega, \mu, \eta, y') \quad i \in \{x, y, z\}$$

where χ_{iz} is non-dimensional stress functions.

$$y' = y/t \quad \leftarrow \text{normalised geometrical parameter}$$

- Resin layer modelling: 2% of H as thickness (revealed parametric study on angle-ply laminate in comparison with literature).

FINITE FRACTURE MECHANICS (FFM) CRITERION

- FFM coupled criterion [4]: $f(\sigma_{ij}(x_i), \sigma_c) \geq 1 \quad \wedge \quad h(\mathcal{G}_g(\Delta a), \mathcal{G}_c) \geq 1$

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} & \frac{2\sigma_\infty}{\pi ab} \int_{-a}^a \int_0^{b/a\sqrt{a^2-x^2}} \sqrt{\left(\frac{\langle \chi_{zz} \rangle}{X_z}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\chi_{zy}}{S_y}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\chi_{zx}}{S_x}\right)^2} dy dx \geq 1 && \longrightarrow \text{Stress criterion} \\ & \frac{2\sigma_\infty^2 h}{\pi ab E'} \geq \frac{\mathcal{G}_c}{\int_{-a}^a \int_0^{b/a\sqrt{a^2-x^2}} (\psi_I^2 + \psi_{II}^2 + \psi_{III}^2) dy dx} && \longrightarrow \text{Energy criterion} \end{aligned} \right.$$

Slave - $E_1^s, E_2^s, G_{12}^s, \nu_{12}^s, \nu_{23}^s$
 Master - $E_1^m, E_2^m, G_{12}^m, \nu_{12}^m, \nu_{23}^m$

Identify	Description
2 non-linear integral system of equations	3 variables: σ_∞, a, b
Interfacial intrinsic parameters (strength & fracture toughness)	$X_z, S_y, S_x; \mathcal{G}_c$
Numerically calculate non-dimensional functions	$\chi_{zz}, \chi_{zy}, \chi_{zx}; \psi_I, \psi_{II}, \psi_{III}$

[4] Leguillon D. Strength or toughness? A criterion for crack onset at a notch. Eur J Mech A/Solids 2002;21:61-72.

HYPOTHESIS: HOMOTHETIC CRACK EXTENSION

- Homothetic crack extension: aspect ratio of crack constant

- 3D-interface semi-elliptical edge crack leads to optimization problem:

Obj function:

$$F_f = \min_{F, \Delta A} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} F \mid f(\sigma_{ij}(x_i), S_x, S_y, X_z) \geq 1 \quad \forall x_i \in \Omega_c \\ \wedge \quad h(G_g(\Delta A), G_{Ic}, G_{IIc}, G_{IIIc}) \geq 1 \end{array} \right\}$$

Constraints:

$$\sigma_\infty(\sigma_{ij}(x_i), S_x, S_y, X_z) = \sigma_\infty(G_g(\Delta A), G_{Ic}, G_{IIc}, G_{IIIc})$$

NORM. IERR OF HERCULES AS1/3501-6

Dependence of ERRs on α and β is due to the crack profile and ply orientation

INTERLAMINAR STRESSES OF HERCULES AS1/3501-6

- Weak singularity is observed at the free edge in interlaminar shear stress.

FAILURE PREDICTION of AS1/3501-6

- Failure load is where stress and energy criteria meets which correspond to minimum load.

Validation of FFM criterion of AS1/3501-6

- FFM predicts precisely the delamination onset evolution within the error bars of tests [6] for each 'n'.
- FFM predicts normalised crack onset width $0.5 \leq \Delta b_f/h \leq 2$ close to 1 which is in accordance to [7].

[6] Brewer JC, Lagace PA. Quadratic stress criterion for initiation of delamination. J Compos Mater 1988;22:1141–55.

[7] Diaz AD, Caron J-F. Prediction of the onset of mode III delamination in carbon/epoxy laminates. Compos Struct 2006;72(4):438–45.

SUMMARY

- Conclusions
 - A method of calculating ERR distribution of semi-elliptical cracks was developed by using 3D-VCCT.
 - Mode-mixity was studied and it was observed that it not only is influenced by polar angle along the crack front but crack profile as well.
 - Similar approach was performed for interlaminar stresses to develop a FFM criterion.
 - Validation of FFM criterion with experimental values indicated very close agreement.
- Future Work
 - Extend current FFM criterion to fatigue scenario (Experimental campaign).

THANK YOU

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